

THE ELASTIC STRESS IN A FIBRE NETWORK IMPREGNATED WITH MOLTEN POLYPROPYLENE

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SUMMARY: A constitutive equation was previously derived for disperse planar fibre networks under transverse compression and validated for *non-impregnated* fibre networks. In this work we apply the equation to a fibre network which has been *impregnated* with a molten polypropylene. Low velocity compression experiments show that the pressure contribution of the fibre network is unchanged by the presence of the liquid polymer and hence that the above equation is applicable to this important case without modification. At sufficiently slow compression rates the fibre network is undisturbed by the liquid which merely flows through it. The limits for this behaviour are also established. The equation successfully predicts the loading response for compression speeds ranging from 10^{-3} to $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s. The viscous contribution of the resin used becomes significant at compression rates above 10^{-3} mm/s, and below $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s exceedingly low responses are observed, possibly due to fibre slippage and rearrangements.

KEYWORDS: elastic stress, compressibility of fibres, discontinuous fibres, disperse planar fibre networks, segregation, fibre slippage, fibre rearrangement, concentrated fibre suspension

INTRODUCTION

Fibre networks are common in applications such as paper processing, felts, filters and reinforcement in composite materials, of which we are particularly interested in the processing of fibre/resin suspensions into composite materials. In all these cases, fibre packing is usually such that the fibre network sustains significant elastic compressive stress. The elastic stress has sometimes to be taken into account in manufacturing processes such as impregnation, consolidation and flow moulding. In these processes the fibre orientation distribution is often planar, or close to planar; and the network, compressed in the direction perpendicular to the plane of orientation, contributes to the stress state of the suspension. Many attempts have been made to model the network stress, notably by van Wyk [1] for 3D fibre networks (wads) and Gutowski [2] for the 1D case (unidirectional fibre beds). Toll and Månson [3] have derived a constitutive model for the 2D case (planar fibre beds). They found a power law relationship between the loading pressure and the fibre volume fraction, where the power law exponent was equal to five. The model successfully described compression data of a planar fibre network.

However, those experiments were all performed "dry," without any liquid resin, which might lubricate the fibre bed and thereby reduce its response. The issue addressed here is whether

the equation by Toll and Månson is valid in the presence of a liquid matrix, such as molten polypropylene in glass mat reinforced thermoplastics (GMT). In order to isolate the packing response of the fibre mat, compression experiments can be performed at low compressive rates, so that the matrix percolates through the fibre bed without inducing any in-plane fibre motion. Kim and McCarthy [4] have investigated the compressibility and relaxation of a stack of impregnated bundle mats with random orientations, and their results are a useful source of comparison to this constitutive equation.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Toll and Månson [3] derived an analytical solution for the elastic compression of a disperse planar fibre network:

$$P = \frac{512}{5\pi^4} E f^4 (\phi^5 - \phi_o^5), \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied pressure, E is the Young's modulus of the fibres, f is a function of the fibre orientation distribution, defined by Toll [5], and ϕ is the fibre volume fraction. The second term, ϕ_o^5 , is a parameter that needs adjustment but tends to be negligible at realistic volume fractions, in which case

$$P = \frac{512}{5\pi^4} E f^4 \phi^5. \quad (2)$$

The derivation of this result is based on the concept that each segment of fibre acts as a bending beam supported by two neighbouring fibres and deflected by a third. Segments of fibre are deflected under a load P . As a segment deflects, it may encounter another fibre. New fibre-fibre contact points are thus continuously generated during compression, making the response highly non-linear. The following assumptions are made about the microstructure:

1. The structure is statistically homogeneous.
2. The fibres are approximately straight and all oriented in the same plane.
3. The fibres are well dispersed in space, in the sense that they do not form bundles.
4. The fibre diameter is uniform.
5. No slippage between fibres occurs.

Two additional assumptions are needed in order to obtain the closed-form result:

6. The incremental force at the fibre-fibre contact points, due to an incremental change in applied load, is uniform.
7. Contact points are randomly distributed along a given fibre.

Although these assumptions appear realistic in the case of a non-impregnated network, assumptions 5 and 6 may or may not hold in the presence of a liquid matrix, lubricating the contact points. If some slippage should occur, the model will predict a too high pressure and the P - ϕ curve will shift towards lower pressure. In addition, any viscous or viscoelastic stresses contributed by the matrix are of course not accounted for by Eqn. 1 and 2. This contribution will add to the network response, shifting the P - ϕ curve towards higher pressure. The elastic response due to the fibre network can, however, be expected to dominate at sufficiently high fibre volume fractions.

Kim and McCarthy [4] have tested various fibre mats mainly made of collimated fibres. As compression speed increases the curve shifts slightly towards higher pressure. Their conclusion was that lower speeds allows more time for fibre rearrangement to occur for non-impregnated networks, and thus requires less load to compress the fibre network. The authors also suggest that lubrication makes the fibre rearrangement easier at low pressures and reduces fibre breakage at high pressures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experiments have been performed using a commercial thermoplastic composite from AZDEL, Inc., with disperse glass fibres and carbon black-filled polypropylene matrix. The fibre length and diameter were 12.7 mm and 12 μm , respectively. The sheets as delivered were semi-consolidated, contained up to 50% voids and had a thickness between 6.1 and 6.5 mm. The influence of air entrapment has been analysed by Leterrier [6], and significant scatter in the material properties and flow results has been mentioned by Ericsson [7]. Fibre weight fractions were obtained by ashing and weighing each specimen after testing. Specimens that deviated significantly from the average in thickness or weight were discarded. Calculations were performed using $\rho_{\text{glass}} = 2.60 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $E_{\text{glass}} = 75 \text{ GPa}$. The in-plane fibre orientation distribution was assumed to be planar random on average, although a slight preferred orientation is known to be present in this material. Thus the value used for the orientation function was that corresponding to planar random orientation, $f = 2/\pi$.

Specimens of $33 \times 33 \text{ mm}^2$ were placed between two 25 mm diameter horizontal parallel plates of a Rheometrics RSA displacement-controlled rheometer as shown in Fig. 1. They were heated to 180°C in an oven until a uniform temperature was reached throughout the thickness; the upper fixture did not touch the specimen during the heating phase. The time of heating was 15 minutes; longer times were also tried but had no effect on the results. The upper plate of the rheometer fixture was then displaced to lightly touch the top of the preform and the initial thickness was recorded. At this moment a small pressure, 20 to 120 Pa, was applied to the sample, and the value of the unloaded fibre volume fraction ϕ_o was extrapolated from that obtained for these small pressures. This volume fraction is somewhat arbitrary since even very small loads may have a strong influence on the sample volume in the melt state, but this procedure only affects the value of ϕ_o , which is unimportant other than at low pressures.

Tests were performed at constant displacement rates ranging between $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and 1 mm/s and the pressure response was recorded. These speeds were sufficiently low so as to cause complete segregation, that is the matrix percolated through motionless fibres and wept out of the specimen as schematically represented in Fig. 1. As a result, the fibre mass contained between the plates was kept constant, and the volume fraction could be directly related to the plate separation.

Fig. 1: The fibre bed is being compressed vertically, but does not flow horizontally, while the resin weeps out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The loading response of lubricated systems shows good correlation with that of previous experiments made on dry fibre beds. Fig. 2 shows the response of an impregnated network compressed at 10^{-3} mm/s and 180°C and that of a dry mat loaded at 0.1 mm/s at room temperature. The two curves superimpose well; so under these conditions no lubrication effect is observed. The compression speed of 10^{-3} mm/s is sufficiently small to ensure that the elastic response of the fibre network dominates. The experiments reported here were performed at 180°C . Changing the temperature to 200°C made no difference; this was also mentioned by Ericsson [7]. No fibre breakage has been detected for the investigated fibre volume fractions.

The elastic network model, Eqn. (1), successfully predicts the loading response for speeds ranging from 10^{-3} to $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s; this is shown in Fig. 3. The experimental data also show good reproducibility. The difference between the theoretical curve and experimental data is within the uncertainty of the fibre orientation distribution. The results in Fig. 3 suggest a slight preferred fibre orientation ($f=0.53$). No effect of the displacement rate, nor of the fibre rearrangement, is detected within the scatter. The unloaded fibre volume fraction ϕ_o was estimated to 0.033, by extrapolation.

Fig. 2: Comparison of the compression behaviour between a lubricated and an ashed fibre network. The temperature is 180°C and the compression speeds are as indicated.

Fig. 3: Loading response of impregnated networks, for speeds ranging from 10⁻³ to 5·10⁻³ mm/s, compared to the prediction of equation (1).

Compression rate effects are detected at rates either below 10⁻³ or above 5·10⁻³ mm/s. It would thus appear that the influence of fibre rearrangement and resin response can be dissociated in this case, appearing in separate rate intervals. The viscous or viscoelastic response of the matrix while it is percolating through the fibre bed could only be detected at speeds exceeding 5·10⁻³ mm/s. This matrix response adds to the network elastic stress leading to higher pressures than for an non-impregnated network. Fibre rearrangements by slippage, on the other hand, is apparent mainly at the lower rates. It probably occurs at all compression rates,

but could only be directly detected from two types of experiment: compression at very low speeds and pressure relaxation.

Fig. 4: Compression behaviour for different speeds ranging from $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to 1 mm/s at 180°C ,
 a) lower and b) higher fibre volume fractions

Fig. 4b shows displacement rate effects at compression rates exceeding $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s. The power law exponent of the relationship between the fibre volume fraction and the packing force tends to decrease slightly as a result of significant matrix response, but is still very close

to five. Also, the pressure tends to increase with increasing speed for a given volume fraction. For reasons of accuracy 1 mm/s could not be exceeded. Fig. 4a shows an even clearer effect of displacement rate at lower fibre volume fractions: the pressure is higher for higher speeds. Differences between higher and lower fibre volume fractions are explained by the dominance of the packing force at higher volume fractions.

At the lowest speeds, $7.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s, the packing force is below that of non-impregnated fibre networks, as shown in Fig. 4b. This is taken as evidence of fibre rearrangement. A similar decrease in the stress response at low velocities was observed by Kim and McCarthy [4]. A general comparison between the model and the above results is presented in Fig. 5. Fibre rearrangement is also detected by pressure relaxation experiments. Relaxation can be observed by recording the pressure once the plates have stopped. A reduction of the packing force with time was also observed by Kim and McCarthy. After 20 minutes the pressure reaches a constant value. The pressure drop, recorded at the highest volume fractions, ranges between 3% and 8 %, but can reach 18% when loading has been performed at the highest speeds. Dry fibre mats do not exhibit stress relaxation. The pressure drop is likely caused by stress relaxation in the matrix and fibre rearrangement. Finally it seems that the fibre rearrangement and viscoelastic response of the matrix are coupled, the latter phenomenon increasing the first: total pressure drop of 18% at the highest speeds.

Fig. 5: General comparison between the model, according to equation (2), and experimental results for all investigated speeds.

The weak influence of the matrix on the loading response for these disperse networks may not be valid for other types of fibre beds. In disperse fibre systems the relatively large contact force at the individual contact points between fibres inhibits fibre motion and renders the characteristics of the impregnated network similar to those of the "dry" case.

CONCLUSION

The packing theory derived for dispersed dry fibre mats can also be applied to commercial lubricated fibre networks. In preform processing, for instance, this work gives a constitutive equation directly related to preform compression. The fibre network response is proportional to fibre volume fraction raised to the power five in all investigated situations. Viscous resistance due to the resin increases the instantaneous loading pressure for compression speeds exceeding $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s, while possible fibre rearrangement decreases this pressure; this phenomenon could be detected during compression at speeds below 10^{-3} mm/s and in relaxation processes when the pressure response is below the one measured for non-impregnated fibre networks, but is thought to always be present.

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